

Processing of plant raw materials using closed-loop technologies to enhance soil quality and safety

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Heavy metal (HM) contamination poses serious risks to soil ecosystems and human health, requiring cost-effective and sustainable remediation strategies. Traditional in-situ and ex-situ remediation techniques often involve costly and environmentally disruptive methods, such as surface capping, encapsulation, landfilling, soil flushing, electrokinetic extraction, solidification, vitrification, phytoremediation [1]. In contrast, HMs stabilization is generally considered as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly approach with rapid effects and at low cost prices [2]. The stabilization method is a remediation technology that uses various non-toxic materials to reduce the solubility of heavy metals in contaminated soils [3]. Among these materials, biochar is a carbon-rich green material that can be applied to stabilize HMs in soils. However, its adsorption performance is highly dependent on the pyrolysis conditions. This study evaluated the effects of pyrolysis conditions on the yield, structural properties, and adsorption capacity of biochar obtained wheat straw.

The pyrolysis of wheat straw was conducted by using a cylindrical reactor under a nitrogen environment to investigate the influence of various pyrolysis conditions on products yield distribution as well as physicochemical characteristics of produced biochars. Based on the obtained data, we identified the optimal pyrolysis conditions for achieving the highest porosity of biochar: temperature 700 °C, retention time 45 min, and heating rate 10 °C/min. The specific surface area of optimized biochar from wheat straw was 72 m²/g with a total pore volume of 0,046 cm³/g.

The efficiency of the developed biochar was investigated in pot experiments in both uncontaminated and metal-contaminated soil. Speciation and redistribution of heavy metals before and after the addition of sorbents to soil was investigated using BCR sequential extraction. Results from the study revealed that after the addition of biochar-based sorbents to soils the metal mobility of Cu, Pb, Zn, and Cd were all drastically reduced, and the effect of stabilization was shown by the transformation of metal from the more available fraction to the more stable oxidizable and residual fractions. The risk assessment code (RAC) decreased, and reduced partition index (IR) increased for all heavy metals with sorbent application, indicating an increase in their fixation strength in soils. X-ray diffraction analysis showed that the biochar effectively stabilized Pb, Cu and Zn in contaminated soils through precipitation processes. Overall, the study highlights the potential of biochar as an advanced soil amendment for sustainable remediation of heavy metal-contaminated soils.

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